

Deliverable D1.1:

Field campaign report

The NuClim field campaign is supported by the Atmospheric Radiation Measurement (ARM) Eastern North Atlantic (ENA) user facility, a U.S. Department of Energy (DOE) Office of Science user facility managed by the Biological and Environmental Research Program

Project NUCLIM received funding from the Euratom research and training programme 2023-2025 under grant agreement No 101166515.

Document information

Project Acronym	NuClim
Project Title	Nuclear observations to improve Climate research and GHG emission estimates
EC grant agreement No.	101166515
Project starting / end date	1st September 2024 – 31 August 2028
Work Package No.	1
Work Package Title	Project management and coordination
Deliverable No.	1.1
Deliverable Title	Field campaign report
Lead Beneficiary	INESC TEC
Contractual Delivery Date	M6 (2025-02-28)
Actual Delivery Date	2025-08-29
Type	R
Dissemination level	PU
Authors	Susana Barbosa, Jussi Paatero, Scott Chambers, Hermanni Aaltonen, Juha Hatakka, Timo Anttila, Nuno Dias, Eduardo Azevedo
To be cited as	
Disclaimer	This document reflects only the author's view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Document status

Date	By	Description
2025-08-01	Susana Barbosa	Document structure; Section 1.1, Section 1.2, Section 1.3.2; Section 4.4; Section 5;
2025-08-23	Scott Chambers	Figures 2 and 3; Figure 8; Section 2;
2025-08-26	Jussi Paatero	Section 1.3.1; Section 4.1, 4.2 and 4.3;
2025-08-26	Juha Hatakka	Section 3;
2025-08-28	Eduardo Azevedo	Review;

Project executive summary

Radon is a unique atmospheric tracer. High-quality direct and indirect measurements of radon concentration can advance climate science, radiation protection and nuclear surveillance. These observations will reduce uncertainty in baseline characterisation of European greenhouse gas (GHG) levels and assist in environmental studies. The EU-funded NuClim project aims to investigate the influence of terrestrial factors on air masses, measure pollution events and explore the impact of natural planktonic communities on GHG emissions. Additionally, it will analyse marine boundary layer clouds and aerosols, and study wet deposition and meteorological processes affecting ambient gamma dose rates for nuclear surveillance networks.

Deliverable executive summary

This deliverable describes NuClim's field campaign, at the ENA-ARM site on Graciosa Island, Azores. The deployment included installation of a GHG observing system, a radon detector, several systems for gamma radiation measurement, and a cluster ion counter. Due to logistical constraints - namely transportation and customs clearance delays - the campaign set-up, initially planned to be concluded on February 2025, was postponed and carried out in two stages: in May 2025 for the GHG component and nuclear measurements performed by FMI, and in July 2025 for the radon detector and ion counter. The installation of all the instruments was completed by July 31st 2025. The NuClim campaign at the ENA-ARM site is now fully functional and ready for continuous operation during the campaign period, planned up to 30 June 2028.

Glossary

ANSTO	Australian Nuclear Science and Technology Organisation
ARM	Atmospheric Radiation Measurement
CIC	Cluster Ion Counter
ENA	Eastern North Atlantic
FMI	Finnish Meteorological Institute, Finland
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GRM	Gamma Radiation Measurement campaign
INESC TEC	Institute for Systems and Computer Engineering, Technology and Science, Portugal
PMT	Photomultiplier Tube
RDM	Radon Detector Monitor software

Table of Contents

1. Introduction.....	9
1.1. Objectives.....	9
1.1.1. Radon measurements.....	9
1.1.2. GHG measurements.....	10
1.1.3. Nuclear measurements.....	10
1.1.4. Ancillary measurements.....	10
1.2. Geographic setting.....	10
1.3. Field layout.....	11
1.3.1. FMI container.....	12
1.3.2. NuClim guest container.....	14
2. Radon detector.....	15
2.1. Instrumentation and set-up.....	15
2.2. Data acquisition.....	18
2.2. Detector tests.....	20
2.2.1. Pressure test.....	20
2.2.2. Background test.....	20
2.2.3. Detector calibration.....	21
2.3. Routine maintenance tasks.....	23
3. GHG observation system.....	24
3.1. Instrumentation and Setup.....	24
3.2. Measurement Protocol and Calibrations.....	25
4. Radon progeny detectors.....	27
4.1. Radon progeny monitor.....	27
4.2. In-situ scintillation gamma spectrometer.....	28
4.3. Dose rate monitor.....	29
4.4. Total gamma radiation counter.....	30
5. Cluster ion counter.....	32
5.1. Instrument set-up.....	32
5.2. Data acquisition.....	34
Acknowledgments.....	35

List of Figures

Figure 1: Location of the field campaign at the ENA ARM observatory.....	9
Figure 2: Location of Graciosa with respect to continental Europe and the Azores archipelago.....	11
Figure 3: Location of the ENA-ARM site on Graciosa Island.....	11
Figure 4: Location at the ENA-ARM site of the containers used in the NuClim campaign.....	12
Figure 5: The FMI's container from the South. The air intake of the sampling line is about 10 m above the ground.....	12
Figure 6: The FMI's container from the North.....	13
Figure 7: Inside view of the FMI's container. The doserate meter and the in-situ gamma spectrometer are on the left, the radon progeny monitor on the right of the back wall, and the greenhouse gas monitor on the right.....	13
Figure 8: Location setting of the NuClim guest container (left) including the 10 m sampling mast and inlet (right).....	14
Figure 9: Schematic drawing of an ANSTO 1500 L two-filter dual flow loop radon detector.....	15
Figure 10: View of the radon detector inside the container at the ENA-ARM site.....	16
Figure 11: Location of radon sampling inlet: external (left) and internal (right).....	17
Figure 12: Radon detector inlet system: sampling blower, water trap and flow bypass.....	17
Figure 13: 400 L delay volume of the 1500 L radon detector for thoron and actinon removal.....	18
Figure 14: General setup of the ENA-ARM radon detector, calibration unit and controlling computer.....	19
Figure 15: Cross checking the calibration of the radon detector's differential pressure sensor with a hand-held differential pressure sensor.....	20
Figure 16: Internal and external views of the calibration and background unit. The internal plumbing has been modified to accommodate a flow-through 8.51 kBq Ra-226 source.....	21
Figure 17: Background measurements at the ENA-ARM site as a function of voltage supplied to PMT.....	21
Figure 18: Czech Metrology Institute flow through calibration source for the radon detector.....	22
Figure 19: G-size cylinder of compressed synthetic air used for the radon detector at the ENA-ARM site....	22
Figure 20: FMI's Graciosa GHG system schematic.....	24
Figure 21: Preliminary hourly average results for CO ₂ (blue), CH ₄ (red) and CO (green) in ppm from May 24 to Aug 21 2025.....	26
Figure 22: Filter/GM tube assemblies of the radon progeny monitor.....	27
Figure 23: Temporal behaviour of the GM tube count rates.....	28
Figure 24: Radon progeny monitor results, 4 June 2025.....	28
Figure 25: In-situ gamma spectrometer components.....	29

Figure 26: An in-situ gamma energy spectrum measured at Graciosa. The peak marked with an arrow is due to the potassium-40 ($E_{\gamma} = 1460$ keV).....	29
Figure 27: Dose rate at Graciosa between 16 June 2025 and 6 July 2025, ten-minute values.....	30
Figure 28: Calibration results for the total gamma radiation counter.....	30
Figure 29: Total gamma radiation measurement system at the ENA-ARM site.....	31
Figure 30: Location of the total gamma radiation counter relative to the radon detector.....	31
Figure 31: Inlets of the CIC counter at the ENA-ARM site.....	32
Figure 32: CIC set-up at the ENA-ARM site.....	33
Figure 33: CIC system installed on the container roof.....	33
Figure 34: Computer controlling the CIC instrument.....	34
Figure 35: CIC configuration file.....	34

1. Introduction

Project NuClim (Nuclear observations to improve Climate research and greenhouse gases (GHG) emission estimates) aims to use high-quality measurements of atmospheric radon activity concentration and ambient radioactivity to advance climate science and to improve radiation protection and nuclear surveillance capabilities. To that end, a field campaign is being conducted to collect high-quality atmospheric measurements of radon and selected GHG concentrations (carbon dioxide (CO₂) and methane (CH₄)) at the Graciosa Island, a remote oceanic location in the middle of the North Atlantic Ocean (Figure 1). The NuClim field campaign is conducted at the Graciosa Eastern North Atlantic (ENA) ARM observatory, a site established and supported by the Department of Energy (DOE) of the United States of America with the collaboration of the regional government and University of the Azores.

This document describes NuClim's field campaign, planned from February 1st 2025 until 30 June 2028. Due to logistical constraints—namely transportation and customs clearance delays—the campaign set-up was postponed and carried out in two stages: in May 2025 for the GHG component and nuclear measurements performed by FMI, and in July 2025 for the radon detector.

Figure 1: Location of the field campaign at the ENA ARM observatory.

1.1. Objectives

1.1.1. Radon measurements

High-quality atmospheric radon activity concentration (referred to as radon) measurements provide an objective means by which to quantify the degree of recent terrestrial influence on marine air masses, and therefore assist diverse climate and environmental studies. The radon-based classification of air mass origin, combined with measurements of aerosols and clouds, enables the characterization of aerosols and cloud properties in relation to the degree of recent terrestrial influence of the host air masses, supporting interpretation of atmospheric observations of trace gases, aerosols, and clouds, and enabling improved quantification of the contributions of both remote terrestrial pollution events and marine biological processes to the composition of the marine atmospheric boundary layer.

1.1.2. GHG measurements

The simultaneous measurement of atmospheric radon concentration and atmospheric carbon dioxide (CO₂) and methane (CH₄) mixing ratios will enable baseline observations of GHGs from marine air masses least influenced by terrestrial sources, representative of hemispheric background values. These observations will enable NuClim to provide an accurate time-varying baseline reference level for European GHG concentrations based on nuclear observations, enabling clearer distinction between local- and regional-scale emissions and slowly changing background levels. Observations performed over NuClim's 40-month duration will constitute the beginning of a highly accurate long-term characterization of trends in mid-latitude Northern Hemisphere baseline concentrations of CO₂ and CH₄, helping to reduce uncertainties in global climate change projections. NuClim will also begin characterizing the seasonality and inter-annual behavior of radon concentrations in the marine boundary layer of the North Atlantic Ocean to assist the evaluation of transport and convective mixing schemes of global climate and chemical transport models.

1.1.3. Nuclear measurements

Indirect measurements of radon, via its particle-bound short-lived progeny, enable studies of radon/radon progeny equilibrium. Furthermore, ambient gamma radiation measurements provide information on the removal of radon progeny from the atmosphere by wet deposition, providing complementary relevant information for atmospheric studies. Improved understanding of wet deposition processes and natural variability driven by meteorological conditions is fundamental for radio-protection and nuclear surveillance applications relying on real-time measurements of the ambient gamma dose rate.

1.1.4. Ancillary measurements

Detailed meteorological, aerosol, and ion measurements enable the use of radon and nuclear data in a range of atmospheric and multidisciplinary environmental applications, including studies of aerosols, cloud properties, and atmospheric pollution events. Chlorophyll observations complement GHG measurements by allowing to assess the marine contribution and relevance of marine organisms to atmospheric CO₂. Laboratory measurements of radon progeny collected on glass-fiber filters enable to obtain relevant information on cosmogenic Be-7 and long-lived Pb-210 radionuclides.

1.2. Geographic setting

Figure 2 shows the geographical location of the ENA-ARM facility with respect to continental Europe. Graciosa island, in the Azores archipelago, is an ideal remote location for atmospheric and marine boundary layer studies. Its small size (61 km²) and low elevation (402 m a.s.l. at its highest point) reduces the likelihood of local island interference with observations of the remote marine boundary layer. Figure 3 shows the location of the ENA site in the north of the island, close to Graciosa airport.

Figure 2: Location of Graciosa with respect to continental Europe and the Azores archipelago.

Figure 3: Location of the ENA-ARM site on Graciosa Island

1.3. Field layout

The NuClim field campaign uses two shipping containers at the ENA-ARM site: a container from FMI, hosting the GHG measurements and FMI's nuclear measurements, and ARM's guest container, which houses the radon detector and other NuClim instruments (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Location at the ENA-ARM site of the containers used in the NuClim campaign.

1.3.1. FMI container

Dr. Hermanni Aaltonen, Mr. Juha Hatakka, Mr. Timo Anttila, and Dr. Jussi Paatero from FMI visited the ENA-ARM station in May 2025 to install instruments for the NuClim measurement campaign. The instruments were installed in a 20 feet sea container which was transported by sea from Finland to Graciosa (Figures 5 - 7).

Figure 5: The FMI's container from the South. The air intake of the sampling line is about 10 m above the ground.

Figure 6: The FMI's container from the North.

Figure 7: Inside view of the FMI's container. The doserate meter and the in-situ gamma spectrometer are on the left, the radon progeny monitor on the right of the back wall, and the greenhouse gas monitor on the right.

Four measurement systems were installed in the FMI container:

1. A greenhouse gas (GHG) monitor,
2. A radon progeny monitor,
3. An in-situ scintillation gamma spectrometer, and
4. A doserate monitor.

The greenhouse gas and radon progeny monitors share a common sampling line with an air intake about 10 m above the ground.

1.3.2. NuClim guest container

The NuClim container (Figure 8) was made available by the ENA-ARM site for housing the NuClim instruments, including:

- atmospheric radon detector
- total gamma radiation counter (NaI(Tl))
- CIC (cluster ion counter)

Figure 8: Location setting of the NuClim guest container (left) including the 10 m sampling mast and inlet (right).

2. Radon detector

2.1. Instrumentation and set-up

The radon detector is a 1500 L dual-flow-loop two-filter radon detector designed by ANSTO and assembled by Colterlec Australia. It was installed and commissioned at the ENA- ARM site between the 28th of July and 1st of August 2025.

Figure 9 presents a schematic of the 1500 L ANSTO two-filter dual flow-loop radon monitor, and Fig. 10 shows a view of the radon detector inside the container at the ENA-ARM site.

Figure 9: Schematic drawing of an ANSTO 1500 L two-filter dual flow loop radon detector.

Figure 10: View of the radon detector inside the container at the ENA-ARM site.

Ambient air for the radon measurements is sampled from an extendable a tower 10 m above ground level. The inlet, comprising 20 mm HDPE pipe inside an inverted 100 mm PVC pipe section with a cap on top, has been designed to minimise direct ingestion of rainfall (the increase in diameter from 20 mm to 100 mm reduces air velocity for carrying droplets). No mesh cover has been placed on the end of the 20 mm pipe, but a disposable coarse filter has been fitted on the upstream side of the stack blower to protect the system against insects and dust. The location of the radon sampling inlet is displayed in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Location of radon sampling inlet: external (left) and internal (right).

The inlet pipe is ducted through the wall of the shipping container near the roof, down the wall, and under the bench. It then passes through a simple water trap before reaching a coarse filter on the inlet of the sampling blower (Fig. 12). Since the blower is operating at a flow rate of several hundred litres per minute flow, and the radon detector only requires a sampling flow rate between 80 and 90 L/min, a flow bypass “T-piece” has been installed to vent the excess sampled air back outside the laboratory. Prior to entering the detector, the sampled air is passed through a delay volume (Fig. 13) such that unwanted isotopes of radon (actinon Rn-219 and thoron Rn-220) have sufficient time to decay to their aerosol progeny.

Figure 12: Radon detector inlet system: sampling blower, water trap and flow bypass.

Figure 13: 400 L delay volume of the 1500 L radon detector for thoron and actinon removal.

2.2. Data acquisition

A commercial data logger (Campbell Scientific Inc. CR300) and Python-based control software (available at <https://github.com/anstoradonlab/>) are used to control detector operation and schedule calibrations. The controlling computer is an industrial PC located on top of the radon detector (Fig. 14). The calibration unit is situated underneath the detector. The data logger and computer communicate via an RS-232 serial connection, direct to COM1 on the industrial PC. The computer and calibration unit communicate via ethernet link. The computer and data logger have been set to UTC time (no daylight savings modification).

Figure 14: General setup of the ENA-ARM radon detector, calibration unit and controlling computer.

The data logger has been programmed to monitor the detector output and associated signals at 10-second intervals, storing totals/averages every 30-minutes (0 and 30 of every hour). The timestamp, along with 16 channels of operational and diagnostic parameters are logged, including internal and external flow rates, raw radon counts and noise counts, the working high voltage setting, differential pressure, etc. The day of month as recorded by the logger is derived from the Julian day (data logger Day of year). The convention for the stored radon data is that the 12:00 saved value represents information collected between 11:30 and 12:00. This should be taken into account when matching the radon data with other data sets (e.g. meteorology).

The radon detector is controlled by a python program called “Radon Detector Monitor” or RDM (version 10.18.0, available from <https://github.com/anstoradonlab/radon-monitor>). This program downloads the logger, manages the logger’s data files, and allows plotting of selected parameters. The main interface screen offers drop-down menus to access some commands as well as four data-table tabs, some plot windows and a system message display box. A status bar at the bottom of the screen provides information about connectivity of RDM to the calibration and background box.

The main functions of the RDM program are:

- Downloading the most recent data from the logger every 10 seconds and 30 minutes.
- Displaying current 10-second and 30-minute data (as columns of ASCII text and as plots).
- Creating and updating monthly data files stored in current and archive directories, and
- Initiating and controlling calibration and background measurements.

2.2. Detector tests

2.2.1. Pressure test

The integrity of the seal around the detector's measurement volume is crucial for the detector's operation, as there is a ~ 2 orders of magnitude difference in concentration of short-lived radon and thoron progeny between ambient boundary layer air and air inside the detector. To counteract inevitable small leaks within the sampling line and detector's delay volume, both should be kept under a slight positive pressure with respect to ambient (usually 100 to 200 Pa).

As part of the detector commissioning process a pressure test was performed after the detector was positioned on the bench in the shipping container, after the detector head had been installed. A hand-held pressure gauge was connected to the T-Piece in the differential pressure line as shown in Figure 15.

Figure 15: Cross checking the calibration of the radon detector's differential pressure sensor with a hand-held differential pressure sensor.

2.2.2. Background test

Even when there is no flow through the detector, it will register a small but quantifiable count rate. This is referred to as the instrumental background. Regular determination of a radon detector's instrumental background at the working voltage is necessary to correctly process the raw data. Furthermore, the instrumental background strongly influences the detector's lower limit of detection.

The calibration and background (C&B) unit of the radon detector at the ENA-ARM site is shown in Figure 16. This unit has been designed to perform automated calibration and background measurements on a working detector at a frequency that is pre-set in the RDM control software, although calibration and background events can also be triggered manually via the RDM control software.

Figure 16: Internal and external views of the calibration and background unit. The internal plumbing has been modified to accommodate a flow-through 8.51 kBq Ra-226 source.

Figure 17 shows background measurements at the ENA-ARM site as a function of working voltage.

Figure 17: Background measurements at the ENA-ARM site as a function of voltage supplied to PMT.

2.2.3. Detector calibration

The Calibration & Background unit of the radon detector (Figure 16) has been designed to routinely perform automatic calibrations on the detector during normal operation without the need of user intervention. Inside the Calibration & Background unit is a Czech Metrology Institute flow through ^{226}Ra source (Serial Number 021024-221545) with an activity of 8.51 (13) kBq ^{226}Ra , which corresponds to a ^{222}Rn delivery rate of 0.9964 (5) Bq min⁻¹. The Calibration & Background unit injects radon-rich air into the detector's gas meter inlet via a 3 mm internal diameter (ID) injection line (Figure 18).

Figure 18: Czech Metrology Institute flow through calibration source for the radon detector.

The Calibration & Background unit to automatically perform calibrations on a monthly basis. A routine calibration (or “calibration event”) involves the injection of radon-rich air to the sample air stream of the operating detector for 5-6 hours, followed by a 5-6 hour detector flushing period to return to ambient concentrations. This process will result in a clearly defined peak in the signal.

Since calibrations are usually only performed once per month, radon can build-up inside the calibration source capsule between calibrations. For this reason, the source is usually flushed prior to starting injection. The source is flushed with a stream of radon-free gas from a compressed cylinder (Fig. 19). Flushing times of 6-8 hours are required.

Figure 19: G-size cylinder of compressed synthetic air used for the radon detector at the ENA-ARM site.

2.3. Routine maintenance tasks

1. Daily:

Check that the RDM logging software is still operational (the last data record should have a timestamp within the past hour), and that diagnostic/operational parameters are within reasonable ranges:

ExFlow:	Sampling flow rate (between 75 – 95 SLPM)
InFlow:	Internal flow velocity (between 11 – 13 m.s ⁻¹)
HV:	High voltage setting (between 770 and 780 V)
LLD:	The plot should show “normal” variability (no spikes or drop-outs).
ULD:	Noise counts. Should be mainly zero (a few counts per day is OK).
TankPPa:	Differential pressure (between 100 and 300 Pa)

2. Weekly:

Check the water trap and empty it if necessary. To empty the water trap, disconnect mains power to the Becker stack blower. Put a tray under the water trap. Open the red ball valve tap to drain the water. Close the tap, then reconnect power to the Becker blower. Make a note in the site log of the date and time.

3. Monthly:

Synchronise the time of the PC clock (which should be network UTC time with no daylight savings) with time on the data logger. In the RDM software, go to the “VIEW” pulldown menu, select “SYSTEM INFORMATION”, press “STOP LOGGING”, press “QUERY PORT” then press “FORCE CLOCK SYNC”, then press the “START LOGGING” button and close the window. (If this process fails, close the RDM program, open up the Campbell Scientific program “Device Configuration Utility” connect to the CR300 logger, and set the logger clock from the appropriate menu. Then close this program, and restart RDM).

Check that the scheduled monthly calibration event has occurred, and the detector returned (automatically) to normal operation. If the scheduled calibration event was missed for any reason (e.g. interruption of power), or there was an obvious problem with the calibration event that did occur, then start a calibration manually from the software menu.

Near the start of each month, make sure that the “c:\data\” directory (and all subdirectories), are backed up to an independent location.

4. Quarterly:

Ensure that the scheduled 3-monthly background event occurred as planned, and the detector has returned to normal operation. If the scheduled event did not occur, start one manually from the software menu .

Check that there is still enough gas left in the compressed gas cylinder for more calibrations. If it is getting low, order a replacement bottle.

Perform a quick, general check, of the detector that all tubing and cables are intact and properly connected. If there is a risk of local birds or insects nesting in the 100 mm PVC inlet pipe, visually inspect the sample inlet on the top of the 10 m mast.

3. GHG observation system

3.1. Instrumentation and Setup

The installed greenhouse gas (GHG) system is based on a cavity ringdown spectrometer (CRDS) Picarro G2401, which measures CO₂, CH₄, CO and water vapor. However, as the sample air is dried with a nafion dryer in reflux-mode, water vapor is usable only for diagnostic purposes.

System includes CRDS-analyzer, nafion dryer for sample air (which also humidifies air from the cylinders), 12-port stream selection rotatory valve, vacuum pump, and five 40 litre high pressure (ca. 200 bar) target/calibration gas cylinders. In addition there are two differential pressure sensors, temperature sensor and sample air flow sensor for diagnostic purposes, see Fig. 20.

Sample air is taken from a high flow rate line (ca. 20 m³/h), which is used for short-lived radon progeny monitor, through a in-line filter and 1/8" SS tubing connected to valve port #1. Sample line's inlet is at 9 m above ground level. Five valve ports are used for the calibration/target cylinders: port #2 for "short term target" (ST) and #6 for "long term target" (LT). Ports 3 - 5 are used for low (C1), medium (C2) and high (C3) mixing ratio calibration cylinders, respectively.

NuClim Graciosa Picarro GHG System Schematic

20: FMI's Graciosa GHG system schematic.

Figure

Calibration and target cylinders were filled and calibrated by FMI (Table 1). Calibrations were made against a 5-cylinder calibration gas set from WMO/CCL (World Meteorological Organization/Central Calibration Laboratory, i.e. NOAA) with Picarro G2401 and G5310 CRDS instruments in January 2025.

Table 1: Calibration/target cylinder mixing ratios.

Cylinder ID	Cylinder Name	CO ₂ (stdev) [ppm]	CH ₄ (stdev) [ppm]	CO (stdev) [ppm]
D856079	C1	385.39 (0.01)	1.9053 (0.0002)	0.0822 (0.0004)
D035685	C2	421.35 (0.01)	2.0727 (0.0001)	0.1752 (0.0004)
D035604	C3	450.98 (0.01)	2.1784 (0.0001)	0.2951 (0.0007)
D035603	LT	436.94 (0.01)	2.1272 (0.0002)	0.1640 (0.0004)
D035673	ST	425.48 (0.01)	2.1031 (0.0002)	0.2052 (0.0005)

The GHG system was installed to a standard 19" rack inside a shipping container, which was acquired, preparatory installations made, and shipped from Finnish Meteorological Institute. The system is connected to FMI's intranet via a 4G-router.

3.2. Measurement Protocol and Calibrations

Short term target (ST) cylinder is used to follow instrument stability by measuring it for 20 minutes every 15 hours. Calibration is made automatically every 15 days (360 hours) starting at 01:00 UTC. This includes measuring cylinders in order: ST, C1, C2, C3, C1, C2, C3, C1, C2, C3, LT, ST each for 25 minutes. First calibration gas (C1,C2,C3) measurements are skipped in processing (flushing period). This protocol is according the one used by ICOS (Integrated Carbon Observation System), but timings (how often, how long each cylinder is measured) are subject to change based on longer term (few months) results.

As the system is measuring always somewhat humid air (sample air dried, cylinder air humidified by nafion), first the instrument readings are converted to dry readings based on the factors determined at FMI. After that a linear calibration equations are determined based on the calibration gas results (C1..C3, last 12 minutes of the 25 minute measurement period) for each component, factors averaged, and interpolated between calibrations. These factors are used to convert dry ambient air readings to dry mixing ratios for each component. Processing is made by first calculating one minute averages, from which one hour averages are further calculated.

Plots of preliminary hourly average results for all the components are depicted in Figure 21.

Figure 21: Preliminary hourly average results for CO₂ (blue), CH₄ (red) and CO (green) in ppm from May 24 to Aug 21 2025

4. Radon progeny detectors

4.1. Radon progeny monitor

Radon-222 is measured via its beta emitting short-lived progeny collected onto a glass-fibre. Sample air is drawn through a filter wrapped around a cylindrical frame. The beta activity accumulating onto the filter is continuously recorded by a cylindrical Geiger–Müller (GM) counter mounted coaxially inside the filter frame (Fig. 22). The filter with the GM tube is located inside a lead shield to reduce the background count rate. The system comprises of two identical filter/GM tube assemblies. A 3-way valve, controlled by a measurement computer, guides the air flow through either of the filter/GM tube assemblies in four-hour periods. The sample air flow rate is about 20 m³/h and it is measured with a mass flow meter. The pulses from the GM counters are recorded, together with air flow data, by a data logger and stored into a computer at one-minute intervals. When the sample air is flowing through a filter, the count rate of the corresponding GM tube increases as beta activity gathers onto the filter (Fig. 22). When the 3-way valve directs the air flow through the other filter assembly, the count rate begins decreasing as the activity on the filter decays. If this activity is due to ²²²Rn progeny only, the count rate returns approximately to the base line during the four-hour period. If, on the other hand, some long-lived activity, such as ²²⁰Rn progeny or artificial activity, is present, the count rate will remain at a higher level after the four-hour decay period. The filters are changed once a week and mailed to the FMI's laboratory for further analysis.

Figure 22: Filter/GM tube assemblies of the radon progeny monitor.

Figure 23: Temporal behaviour of the GM tube count rates.

An example of radon progeny results (4 June 2025) is depicted in Fig. 24. Compared to continental sites the radon activity concentrations are low at Graciosa.

Figure 24: Radon progeny monitor results, 4 June 2025.

4.2. In-situ scintillation gamma spectrometer

The in-situ scintillation gamma spectrometer consists of a 76 mm x 76 mm NaI(Tl) scintillation detector, a PMT base/preamplifier, a HV supply/linear amplifier unit, a multichannel analyser and a measurement

computer (Fig. 25). The energy spectrum of the ambient gamma radiation from 100 keV to 3000 keV is recorded in one-hour resolution. An example of a one-hour long measurement is depicted in Fig. 26.

Figure 25: In-situ gamma spectrometer components.

Figure 26: An in-situ gamma energy spectrum measured at Graciosa. The peak marked with an arrow is due to the potassium-40 ($E_\gamma = 1460$ keV).

4.3. Dose rate monitor

External dose rate in the air caused by cosmic radiation, gamma radiation from the ground and airborne and deposited gamma emitters is measured with a dose rate monitor connected to the measurement computer of the in-situ gamma spectrometer. The dose rate monitor is equipped with two GM tubes, one for normal ambient dose rate levels and one for very high dose rate levels associated with nuclear accidents etc. The dose rate is very stable at Graciosa varying between 0.06 and 0.08 $\mu\text{Sv/h}$ (Fig. 27).

Figure 27: Dose rate at Graciosa between 16 June 2025 and 6 July 2025, ten-minute values.

4.4. Total gamma radiation counter

A total gamma radiation counter has been operating at ENA since May 2015 for the GRM campaign, and it will also be used in the NuClim campaign, thereby extending the available time series of total gamma radiation observations.

The instrument is a NaI(Tl) scintillation of 3"×3" (Scionix, Holland) equipped with an electronic total count Single Channel Analyzer (SCA) measuring gamma radiation from 475 keV to 3000 keV. Calibration results from the manufacturer are displayed in Figure 28. The measurement set-up at the ENA-ARM station is shown in Figure 29. The detector is installed at the back of the guest container (Figure 30).

Figure 28: Calibration results for the total gamma radiation counter.

Figure 29: Total gamma radiation measurement system at the ENA-ARM site.

Figure 30: Location of the total gamma radiation counter relative to the radon detector.

5. Cluster ion counter

5.1. Instrument set-up

The cluster ion counter (CIC), from Airel (Estonia) uses two independent first order cylindrical differential mobility analyzers to measure the ions of positive and negative polarities in parallel. The measured ions entering the analyzers are repelled by a central electrode which is held at a steady voltage. Charged particles deposit on the outer wall of the analyser which is divided into three separate collecting electrodes. The electric current produced by the deposited ions is measured using high precision integrating electrometers.

The instrument was refurbished and calibrated by the manufacturer on November 2024, and installed at the ENA-ARM site on July 30th 2025. Detailed installation instructions at <https://drive.inesctec.pt/s/kG6a4mydW2xy2Sy>.

The USB interface originally installed by the manufacturer was replaced with an RS232 connection to accommodate longer distances from the logging computer.). The instrument has two inlets in the front (positive and negative) and two outlets in the back with pumps that can have a flow rate from from 10 L to 60 L/min. The two inlet pipes are chrome-plated copper tubes, 80 cm long and 30 mm in diameter, curved down to avoid rain. A metal mesh size with 1 mm² size is placed on the end of the inlet tube to keep insects out (Fig. 31). The sensor is housed inside a case (PELI 1550) which was drilled to accommodate the inlets/outlets and cables (Fig.32). The case is installed on the roof of the shipping container, securely attached with straps, and the cables connect to the controlling computer inside the container (Fig. 33).

Figure 31: Inlets of the CIC counter at the ENA-ARM site.

Figure 32: CIC set-up at the ENA-ARM site.

Figure 33: CIC system installed on the container roof.

5.2. Data acquisition

The CIC instrument is connected by an Cat6E Ethernet cable with a RJ45 to RS232 converter to an industrial computer (TeraSystem with 4 GB of RAM and SSD with 512 GB), located inside the container (Fig. 34). Spectops and Spectops-cli, the software provided by the instrument manufacturer, is installed in the computer running Ubuntu 24.04 LTS operating system. The configuration file used by the software to connect to the sensor is shown in Fig. 35. The program spectops-cli is started when the computer boots.

Each day a new set of four data files are generated

- yyyyymmdd.log – program log;
- yyyyymmdd-1s.records – 1 second data collected;
- yyyyymmdd-10s.records – 10 second data collected;
- yyyyymmdd-block.records – block records of data

Figure 34: Computer controlling the CIC instrument.

```

averaging_periods: [1, 10]
inverters: ''
measurement:
  auto_discover: false
  network_address: 127.0.0.1
  passive_mode: false
  sequence:
  - [ions, 90]
  - [offset, 30]
  serial_port: /dev/ttyS0
output:
  path: /home/inesctec/cic/data/
  save_averages: [1, 10]
  save_block_averages: true
  save_raw: false
spectrometer: cic-6-instrument
    
```

Figure 35: CIC configuration file.

Acknowledgements

The NuClim field campaign is supported by the Atmospheric Radiation Measurement (ARM) Eastern North Atlantic (ENA) user facility, a U.S. Department of Energy (DOE) Office of Science user facility managed by the Biological and Environmental Research Program.

Support from the ARM staff at ENA, Bruno Cunha and Tercio Silva, is gratefully acknowledged.